

Free Vibration Analysis of Orthotropic Composite Triangular Plates

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Abstract

A very simple and computationally efficient numerical method is developed for the free vibration analysis of isotropic and orthotropic triangular plates. A set of two-dimensional simple series functions is used as admissible displacement functions in the Rayleigh-Ritz method to obtain natural frequencies, nodal patterns and mode shapes for the plates. From the prescribed starting function satisfying only geometric boundary conditions, the higher terms in the polynomial series functions are constructed by increasing the order of the polynomial. Natural frequencies, nodal patterns and mode shapes are obtained for right triangular plates with three different support conditions. Some numerical results for isotropic and orthotropic plates are presented and compared with other numerical solutions available in the literature.

Keywords : Vibration; Simple Series Function; Triangular Plates;
Composite Materials; Natural Frequency; Mode Shapes; Nodal Patterns

1. INTRODUCTION

Flexural vibration studies on the plates with various shapes and configurations are well documented in the report by Leissa[1]. Although the finite element method has become one of the most popular techniques with the rapid advancement in computer technology, it usually is expensive to obtain the vibration responses of plates. To overcome the shortcomings of the finite element method, the several numerical and analytical methods for the vibration analysis of triangular plates were developed and published in the literatures[3]-[7]. Gorman[3] proposed an analytical technique based on superposition of building blocks for free vibration analysis of triangular plates. A gridwork method was used by Christensen[4] to analyze the free vibrations of cantilevered triangular plates. Bhat[5] used Rayleigh-Ritz method to solve cantilevered triangular plate problems with different plate geometries. A set of two-dimensional orthogonal plate functions was recently developed by Lam[6], to analyse free vibrations of plates with various geometries. Lam[6] employed this method to solve isotropic and orthotropic triangular plate problems with various boundary conditions. In the present paper, a set of simple series functions is constructed to study the vibration behaviour of triangular plates by Rayleigh-Ritz method. This simple series functions do not require to meet the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization relationship. Various combinations of boundary conditions for the triangular plates are considered. To demonstrate the procedure of the present method, the natural frequencies, nodal patterns and mode shapes of the plates are presented.

2. ASSUMED DISPLACEMENT FUNCTION

The out-of-plane displacement function for a vibrating triangular plate shown in Fig.1 can be defined, by a set of two-dimensional simple series plate functions, as

$$W(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta), \quad (1)$$

where $\xi = X/a$, $\eta = Y/b$, and m denotes the total number of terms retained in the set. The starting admissible function, $\phi_1(\xi, \eta)$, chosen for the triangular plate must satisfy at least the geometrical boundary conditions of the plate, although better convergence can be achieved, if it also satisfies natural boundary conditions. The function, $\phi_1(\xi, \eta)$, originally used in Reference[6], can be written as

$$\phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \prod_{n=1}^3 \phi_n(\xi, \eta) \quad (2)$$

where Π denotes the product of subsequent terms and ϕ_n 's are the edge functions which can be easily formulated if the support condition of the plate edge is known. The function $\phi(\xi, \eta)$ for different boundary conditions are summarized as the Equations 3-5 presented below.

(a) for simply supported edge

$$\phi(\xi, \eta) = \begin{cases} \xi - c & \text{along } \xi = c \\ \eta - d & \text{along } \eta = d \\ \eta - t\xi - e & \text{along } \eta = t\xi + e, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

(b) for clamped edge

$$\phi(\xi, \eta) = \begin{cases} (\xi - c)^2 & \text{along } \xi = c \\ (\eta - d)^2 & \text{along } \eta = d \\ (\eta - t\xi - e)^2 & \text{along } \eta = t\xi + e, \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

(c) for free edge

$$\phi(\xi, \eta) = 1. \quad (5)$$

The higher terms ($m > 2$) in the displacement function 1 can be generated by the following recurrence relation,

$$\phi_m(\xi, \eta) = f_m(\xi, \eta) \phi_1(\xi, \eta) \quad (m = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (6)$$

where $f_m(\xi, \eta)$ is the generation functions shown in Table 1. The generated plate function $\phi_m(\xi, \eta)$ has to satisfy geometrical boundary conditions but does not require to satisfy the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization relationship. To demonstrate the procedure of forming these orthogonal plate functions, the first six terms of $f(\xi, \eta)$ and $\phi(\xi, \eta)$ are presented in Table 1.

3. ANALYSIS METHOD

The approximate solutions for the free vibration analysis of a thin triangular plate shown in Fig.1 can be derived by the principle of minimum potential energy. The total potential energy, π , of the plate can be written as

$$\pi = U_{\max} - T_{\max} \quad (7)$$

where U and T denote the strain and kinetic energy of the system, respectively. For small-amplitude vibration, the strain energy for an orthotropic triangular plate can be obtained to be, as a function of the admissible function in Equation 1,

Table 1. First six simplified series functions for C-F-F isosceles right triangular plates.

Generating -functions	Simple series -plate functions
$f_1(\xi, \eta) = 1$	$\phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \eta^2$
$f_2(\xi, \eta) = \xi$	$\phi_2(\xi, \eta) = \xi \phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \xi \eta^2$
$f_3(\xi, \eta) = \eta$	$\phi_3(\xi, \eta) = \eta \phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \eta^3$
$f_4(\xi, \eta) = \xi \eta$	$\phi_4(\xi, \eta) = \xi \eta \phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \xi \eta^3$
$f_5(\xi, \eta) = \xi^2$	$\phi_5(\xi, \eta) = \xi^2 \phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \xi^2 \eta^2$
$f_6(\xi, \eta) = \eta^2$	$\phi_6(\xi, \eta) = \eta^2 \phi_1(\xi, \eta) = \eta^4$

Fig. 1 Geometry and coordinate system

$$U_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} ab \left\{ \iint_R \frac{D_{11}}{a^4} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} \right]^2 + \frac{2D_{12}}{a^2 b^2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial^2 \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} \right] + \frac{D_{22}}{b^4} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} \right]^2 + \frac{4D_{66}}{a^2 b^2} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} \right]^2 \right\} d\xi d\eta \quad (8)$$

Similarly, the kinetic energy of the triangular plate can be written as

$$T_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \rho h ab \omega^2 \iint_R \left[\sum_{i=1}^m C_i \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \right]^2 d\xi d\eta \quad (9)$$

In the Equations 8 and 9, D_{ij} denotes bending stiffnesses, ρ the material density, h the plate thickness, and ω frequency parameter. Using the principle of minimum potential energy and substituting the Equations 8 and 9 into the Equation 7, following system of characteristic equations can be obtained.

$$[K_{ij} - \lambda_0 M_{ij}] C_i = 0 \quad (10)$$

where

$$K_{ij} = D'_{11} P_{ij} + \alpha^4 D'_{22} Q_{ij} + 2\alpha^2 D'_{12} (R_{ij} + S_{ij}) + 4\alpha^2 D'_{66} T_{ij} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} M_{ij} &= \iint_R \phi_i(\xi, \eta) \phi_j(\xi, \eta) d\xi d\eta, & P_{ij} &= \iint_R \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_j(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} d\xi d\eta \\ Q_{ij} &= \iint_R \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_j(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} d\xi d\eta, & R_{ij} &= \iint_R \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_j(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} d\xi d\eta \\ S_{ij} &= \iint_R \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_j(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \eta^2} d\xi d\eta, & T_{ij} &= \iint_R \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_j(\xi, \eta)}{\partial \xi \partial \eta} d\xi d\eta \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\lambda_0 = \rho h \omega^2 a^4 / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}, \quad \alpha = a/b \quad (13)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} D'_{11} &= D_{11} / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}, & D'_{12} &= D_{12} / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}} \\ D'_{22} &= D_{22} / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}}, & D'_{66} &= D_{66} / \sqrt{D_{11} D_{22}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

By solving the characteristic Equation 10, such responses as natural frequencies, related mode shapes and nodal patterns of the triangular plate can be finally obtained.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Several numerical examples are considered to demonstrate the validity and accuracy of the proposed method. Material properties of isotropic and orthotropic composite materials are given in Table 2. In this paper, the free vibration responses of the plates are presented in the form of nondimensional frequency parameter, λ , which is defined as

Table 2. Material properties of typical unidirectional composites⁽⁶⁾.

Material	E_1/E_2	G/E_2	ν_{12}
Isotropic	1.00	0.3846	0.30
Glass-epoxy	4.67	0.50	0.26
Boron-epoxy	11.03	0.30	0.23
Kevlar-epoxy	13.82	0.42	0.34
Graphite-epoxy	17.57	0.70	0.28

$$\lambda = \frac{(\lambda_0)^{1/2}}{2\pi} = \frac{\omega a^2 (\rho h)^{1/2}}{2\pi (D_{11} D_{22})^{1/4}} \quad (15)$$

Isosceles right triangular plates with three different support conditions are considered in the analysis, namely: (a) simply supported (S-S-S), (b) all edges clamped (C-C-C), (c) cantilevered (C-F-F).

4.1. Convergence of the frequency parameter

It is known that the energy approach provides an upper-bound to the exact solution. In order to achieve a proper convergence, numerical calculation is performed by varying the number of terms used in the displacement function. Table 3 summarizes the convergence pattern of the isotropic plates with three different boundary conditions. Table 3 shows that the convergence is achieved if more than 20 terms are retained for the displacement function 1. The nondimensionalised frequency parameters obtained by the present method are compared with those by Lam[6]. It is formed that the present frequency parameter is 1-8% smaller for the C-F-F case and 2-7% larger for the S-S-S case than those presented by Lam[6].

Table 3. Convergence patterns of the nondimensional frequency parameter λ of isotropic isosceles right triangular plates, for three boundary conditions.

Mode Number	For boundary condition C-F-F, Number of series term = m								
	8	12	16	18	20	24	26	28	30
1	0.96 (0.98)	0.95 (0.98)	0.94 (0.98)	0.94 (0.98)	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94
2	3.95 (3.92)	3.68 (3.77)	3.67 (3.73)	3.67 (3.73)	3.66	3.66	3.66	3.66	3.66
3	4.92 (5.39)	4.86 (5.24)	4.83 (5.21)	4.82 (5.21)	4.82	4.82	4.82	4.81	4.81
4	10.73 (10.88)	9.46 (9.51)	8.78 (9.43)	8.65 (9.41)	8.60	8.59	8.58	8.57	8.56
Mode	For boundary condition S-S-S								
1	8.42 (8.05)	8.42 (7.88)	8.23 (7.85)	8.22 (7.85)	8.22	8.22	8.22	8.22	8.22
2	19.84 (19.34)	16.93 (16.48)	16.62 (15.94)	16.35 (15.66)	16.23	16.20	16.17	16.14	16.14
3	27.10 (25.97)	22.92 (21.62)	22.46 (21.08)	21.94 (20.46)	21.84	21.81	21.76	21.72	21.72
4	49.64 (48.88)	36.47 (35.56)	31.02 (28.74)	28.73 (27.38)	28.39	27.94	27.77	27.58	27.43
Mode	For boundary condition C-C-C								
1	15.54	15.50	15.49	15.48	15.48	15.47	15.47	15.47	15.47
2	26.51	26.14	26.01	25.92	25.84	25.83	25.83	25.82	25.82
3	33.70	32.83	32.66	32.58	32.56	32.55	32.54	32.53	32.53
4	47.34	42.24	40.72	39.99	39.97	39.78	39.71	39.60	39.53

()--Ref⁽⁶⁾

4.2 Frequency responses

The frequency parameter obtained by the present method for the plates with different boundary conditions and material systems are summarized in Tables 4-6, along with the results available in the literature.

(a) *Cantilevered plate.* The frequency parameters of the cantilevered plate are summarized in Table 4. The present numerical results for the isotropic plate are compared with available experimental results[8] and numerical ones by Mirza[4], Bhat[5], Lam[6] and Kim[7]. It is observed that the present method yields slightly lower frequencies than other numerical results. However, the agreement is better when compared with experimental result[8]. It is also found that the results by the present method are identical to the ones by Lam[6] for orthotropic triangular plates.

Table 6. Comparison of the nondimensional frequency parameter λ of all clamped supported (C-C-C) isosceles right triangular plates.

Material	Reference	Mode Number					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Isotropic	Present	15.47	25.82	32.53	39.53	46.15	56.58
	Kim ⁽⁷⁾	(14.93)	(25.12)	(31.00)	(38.69)	(44.28)	(53.52)
Glass-epoxy	Present	14.97	24.49	31.51	36.83	44.89	53.39
Boron-epoxy	Present	15.12	23.74	32.17	35.26	44.83	51.21
Kevlar-epoxy	Present	15.62	24.24	33.34	37.03	46.23	52.05
Graphite-epoxy	Present	16.12	24.70	34.30	36.92	47.48	52.86

4.3 Nodal patterns

The nodal patterns of the second through sixth vibration mode of the isotropic and several orthotropic plates with three different boundary conditions are given in Figs 2-4, respectively.

(a) *Cantilevered plate.* The nodal patterns of plates with boundary condition C-F-F are given in Fig.2. The figure shows excellent agreement in the nodal patterns for the second, third and fourth mode of isotropic plate obtained by the present authors and by Leissa[1], Bhat[5], Lam[6] and Kim[7]. It is also observed nodal patterns by present method are finer than those obtained by Bhat[5] in the fifth and sixth vibration modes. Though the frequency parameter, λ , of the plates with orthotropic materials is half of that of the plates with isotropic material, the nodal patterns of the plates with orthotropic material are found to be slightly different from those with the isotropic material. The nodal lines of the vibration modes of the plates with orthotropic material are along the direction of fiber.

Fig. 2. Nodal patterns for C-F-F isosceles right triangular plates: (a) isotropic ($E_1/E_2=1.0$), (b) glass-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=4.63$), (c) boron-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=11.03$), (d) kevlar-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=13.82$), (e) graphite-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=17.57$)

Fig. 3. Nodal patterns for S-S-S isosceles right triangular plates: (a) isotropic ($E_1/E_2=1.0$), (b) glass-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=4.63$), (c) boron-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=11.03$), (d) kevlar-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=13.82$), (e) graphite-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=17.57$)

The frequency parameters for orthotropic material is observed to be 20~45% lower than those for isotropic material, in which case the direction of fiber runs parallel to the clamped edge.

(b) *Simply supported plate.* Table 5 presents the frequency parameters of the simply supported plates obtained by the present method and those by Gorman [5], Lam[6], and Kim[7]. From table 5, it can be seen that the agreement is reasonably good. The fundamental frequency parameter by the present method for isotropic plates is observed to be 6% higher than the one by Lam[6]. However, only less than 3% of difference is observed between the results for the orthotropic material systems.

(c) *All clamped plate.* The frequency parameters of the C-C-C right triangular plate are given in Table 6. The results obtained for the isotropic triangular plate are observed to be 3~6% higher than the solutions by Kim[7]. To the author's knowledge, other published results for the orthotropic C-C-C plates are not available and the frequency parameter of orthotropic material is not made. However, it is observed that the frequency parameters between isotropic and orthotropic plates are almost the same between them.

Table 4. Comparison of the nondimensional frequency parameter λ of a cantilever supported (C-F-F) isosceles right triangular plates.

Material	Reference	Mode Number					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Isotropic	Present	0.94	3.66	4.81	8.56	11.60	15.40
	Mirza ⁽²⁾	(0.98)	(3.67)	(5.30)	(8.90)	(11.86)	(15.83)
	Bhat ⁽⁵⁾	(0.98)	(3.74)	(5.21)	(8.98)	(12.45)	(17.16)
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(0.98)	(3.73)	(5.21)	(9.41)		
	Kim ⁽⁷⁾	(0.98)	(3.73)	(5.20)	(8.94)	(12.18)	(15.93)
	Experiment ⁽⁸⁾	(0.92)	(3.64)	(5.09)	(8.70)	(11.81)	(15.48)
Glass-epoxy	Present	0.69	2.80	3.93	6.94	9.58	13.21
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(0.69)	(2.81)	(4.03)	(6.99)		
Boron-epoxy	Present	0.54	2.13	3.05	5.44	7.50	10.61
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(0.54)	(2.10)	(3.12)	(5.58)		
Kevlar-epoxy	Present	0.52	2.12	3.03	5.32	7.46	10.35
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(0.52)	(2.13)	(3.09)	(5.46)		
Graphite-epoxy	Present	0.51	2.13	3.21	5.28	7.83	10.27
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(0.51)	(2.14)	(3.26)	(5.69)		

Table 5. Comparison of the nondimensional frequency parameter λ of all simply supported (S-S-S) isosceles right triangular plates.

Material	Reference	Mode Number					
		1	2	3	4	5	6
Isotropic	Present	8.22	16.14	21.72	27.43	33.56	42.51
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(7.85)	(15.66)	(20.46)	(27.38)		
	Kim ⁽⁷⁾	(7.86)	(15.72)	(20.44)	(26.91)	(31.88)	(38.76)
	Gorman ⁽³⁾	(7.85)	(15.64)	(20.45)	(27.31)		
Glass-epoxy	Present	7.74	15.12	20.58	25.49	32.30	40.44
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(7.57)	(15.01)	(20.21)	(27.26)		
Boron-epoxy	Present	7.58	14.21	20.81	23.71	32.09	40.56
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(7.47)	(14.29)	(20.65)	(26.37)		
Kevlar-epoxy	Present	7.85	14.48	21.72	24.09	33.20	41.52
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(7.71)	(14.52)	(21.54)	(27.04)		
Graphite-epoxy	Present	8.10	14.70	22.50	24.52	34.22	42.54
	Lam ⁽⁶⁾	(8.01)	(14.11)	(22.61)	(27.73)		

(b) *Simply supported plate.* Fig.3 shows the nodal patterns for S-S-S plates. This figure shows that the mode shapes for isotropic and graphite plate obtained by the present authors and by Lam[6] and Kim[7]. As can be seen, however, the presented nodal patterns show apex effect. Moreover, the apex effect for the isotropic material system is symmetric and small. As the degree of orthotropy, E_1/E_2 increases, the apex effect becomes clearer and more unsymmetric.

(c) *All clamped plate.* The nodal patterns for C-C-C plates are given in Fig.4. The agreement of the mode shapes for isotropic plate between the present authors and those obtained by Kim[7] is very good. Though the frequency parameter λ of the C-C-C plates is only half of those of the S-S-S plates, the nodal patterns are found to be almost the same as those for the S-S-S plates. The apex effect of the C-C-C plates is clearer as compared to the S-S-S boundary condition.

Fig. 4. Nodal patterns for C-C-C isosceles right triangular plates: (a) isotropic ($E_1/E_2=1.0$), (b) glass-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=4.63$), (c) boron-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=11.03$), (d) kevlar-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=13.82$), (e) graphite-epoxy ($E_1/E_2=17.57$)

Fig. 5. Mode shapes for isotropic C-F-F isosceles right triangular plates, with mode 1-6. (axis rotating angle: $X=24^\circ$, $Y=-24^\circ$, $Z=0^\circ$, nonscale of deflection)

Fig. 6. Mode shapes for boron-epoxy C-F-F isosceles right triangular plates, with mode 1-6. (axis rotating angle: $X=24^\circ$, $Y=24^\circ$, $Z=0^\circ$, nonscale of deflection)

4.4 Mode shapes

The first six mode shapes of the isotropic and boron-epoxy triangular plates for C-F-F, S-S-S and C-C-C boundary conditions are given in Figs. 7~10. Fig.7 shows the mode shapes of C-F-F isotropic isosceles right triangular plates. It can be seen that the agreement in the mode shapes by the present authors and by Mirza[2] is very good. Fig.8 shows the mode shapes for C-F-F boron-epoxy isosceles right triangular plates. Though the frequency parameter of the boron-epoxy is half of that of an isotropic plate, the mode shapes are observed to be quite the similar. Fig.9 and 10 shows the mode shapes of isotropic S-S-S and C-C-C plates, respectively. Though the deflection figures of the mode shapes, can be supposed from the nodal pattern. The presented figures of the mode shapes arouse interest in the eye-sight. The mode shapes of C-C-C plates are found to be almost the same as those of S-S-S plates, except the effect of clamed edges extends the deformed shapes. The mode shapes of orthotropic plates are observed to be almost the same as those of isotropic plates which are not shown in this paper.

Fig. 7 Mode shapes for isotropic S-S-S isosceles right triangular plates with mode 1~6 (axis rotating angle : $X=24^\circ$, $Y=-24^\circ$, $Z=0^\circ$, nonscale of deflection)

Fig. 8 Mode shapes for isotropic C-C-C isosceles right triangular plates with mode 1~6 (axis rotating angle : $X=24^\circ$, $Y=-24^\circ$, $Z=0^\circ$, Nonscale of deflection)

5. CONCLUSION

A set of simple polynomial type series functions is used as admissible plate functions in the Rayleigh-Ritz procedure to predict the natural frequencies, nodal patterns and mode shapes for isotropic and orthotropic right triangular plates with different boundary conditions. Based on the numerical results, following conclusions are drawn

1. A simple series plate functions can accurately predict the free vibration responses of the plates.
2. The present method can be used to approach vibration analysis of plates with arbitrary shape being describe to the functions, for which is very simple, for which time and efforts can be saved.
3. The predicted results by the present method in general, show good agreement with the results available in the literature. It is shown that converged solutions can be obtained when more than 20 terms of the displacement functions are used.
4. The predicted nodal patterns and mode shapes for the plates by the present method agree well with those available in the literature. It is observed that although the natural frequencies between isotropic and orthotropic plates are different, the nodal patterns and mode shapes of the plates are very similar between them.

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